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FWS No. 14-16-0009-87

GRANT AGREEMENT
BETWEEN
U.S. FISH AND WILDLIFE SERVICE
AND
THE NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF COSTA RICA

We, Carlos Araya Pochet, of age, married, of Tibas, Costa Rica, Dr. of History, Identification No. 9015901, as Rector of the National University, further referred to as UNA; and Janet Wildman, of age, married, of Gaithersburg, Maryland, United States of America, as Contracting Officer, Branch of Contracting of the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service of the Department of the Interior of the Government of the United States of America, further referred to as USFWS, agree to fulfill the following grant between the USFWS and the UNA:

I. PURPOSE, AUTHORITY, AND BACKGROUND

The U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service received an appropriation in Fiscal Year 1987 to assist U.S. implementation of the Convention on Nature Protection and Wildlife Preservation in the Western Hemisphere. The priority action needs identified by the Congress authorize implementation activities related to training of Latin American personnel in the management of wildlife and protected area habitats. The National University of Costa Rica shares an interest in implementing the Convention, conducts the most important wildlife management training program in Latin America, and possesses strong staff expertise for this program area.

This Grant from the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, Department of the Interior, hereinafter referred to as USFWS, to the National University of Costa Rica, hereinafter referred to as UNA, is hereby entered into under the authority of the Endangered Species Act of 1973, as amended (16 U.S.C. 1531-43). This agreement will enable UNA to administer projects within the Western Hemisphere program.

All work is to be performed in accordance with Appendix 1 "Statement of Work."

II. SCOPE OF WORK

Specifically, the USFWS will:

1. Provide Fiscal Year 1987 funds not to exceed \$58,000 to UNA for the continued development of the graduate program in wildlife management.

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Specifically, the UNA will:

1. Provide graduate level training in wildlife management to biologists from throughout Latin America and the Caribbean.
2. Acknowledge the contribution of the "Office of International Affairs, U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service" in any announcement, release, article, report, or other printed material relating to this activity. Where appropriate the USFWS logo will be displayed.
3. Submit to the USFWS Project Officer a annual status report on the activities which have received support under this agreement and the level of support for each.

III. FINANCIAL ADMINISTRATION

1. The total funds made available under this Grant is \$58,000.
2. UNA may invoice for \$10,000 immediately upon the effective date of the agreement by requesting such payment in a letter to the USFWS project officer stating the proper payee and listing the mailing address. The letter shall reference the FWS Grant number. All invoices shall include a reference to FWS Grant No. 14-16-0009- _ _ _ , and shall be sent directly to:

Office of International Affairs
U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service
Department of the Interior, Room 2058
18th & "C" Streets, NW
Washington, DC 20240

Subsequent invoices shall be submitted not more frequently than monthly.

3. All funds provided by USFWS under this agreement shall be deposited with the "Fundacion-UNA." Interest generated from these deposited funds will belong to the Fundacion-UNA.
4. Funds are to be expended as indicated in the attached budget (Appendix 2). The Director of the Graduate Program in Wildlife Management (School of Environmental Sciences), with the prior approval of the Budget Committee of that program, will be in charge of funds disbursements. A change of expenditure totals of more than 10% between categories in the budget must be approved by the USFWS Project Officer.

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5. The FWS and UNA will consider jointly all potential expenditures and activities relating to this agreement.

IV. PROJECT OFFICERS

USFWS: Dr. Herbert A. Raffaele
Office of International Affairs
U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service
Department of the Interior
Room 2058
18th & "C" Street, NW
Washington, DC 20240
(202) 343-5188

UNA: Prof. Christopher Vaughan
Escuela de Ciencias Ambientales
Apartado 86
Universidad Nacional Autónoma
Heredia, Costa Rica

V. EQUIPMENT

Equipment acquired under this grant becomes the property of UNA and will remain with UNA for continued use in its graduate program in wildlife management.

VI. DURATION, MODIFICATION AND TERMINATION

This Grant shall be effective upon the date of last signature through the expiration date of September 30, 1988. This agreement may be extended on an annual basis not to go beyond September 30, 1993, subject to mutual agreement of both parties and the availability of funds. Either party may unilaterally terminate this agreement by providing written notice to the other at least 90 days in advance of the proposed termination date. X

X In agreement with the above, we sign three originals in English and three in Spanish in the City of Washington, D.C., on the _____ day of _____ and in Heredia, on the _____ day of _____ of Nineteen Eighty-seven.

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STATEMENT OF WORK

Project Description1. Master of Science Degree in Wildlife Management

Of all the components in the management process, the proper training of personnel is one of the most decisive factors in determining whether a country is able to establish and appropriately manage a system of wildlands or wildlife conservation units. To provide for such training the National University of Costa Rica (UNA) in cooperation with the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (USFWS) and the World Wildlife Fund, initiated in 1985 the first graduate level training program in wildlife management.

The overall objective of the program is to provide critically needed training in a broad range of skills necessary for the professional wildlife biologist. The UNA program is specifically designed to meet the needs of biologists from Latin America.

The first class of one dozen students representing eight Latin American countries is already underway and appears to be moving along very successfully. A second class of students has already been selected and will begin studies in February 1988.

Through this project assistance will be provided to the graduate program primarily to:

- Provide scholarships for Latin American students in the program;
- Support thesis research projects;
- Provide honoraria for visiting professors;
- Enhance other components of the graduate program agreed to by both parties.

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APPENDIX 2

BUDGET
For the Graduate Program in Wildlife Management

	<u>FWS</u>
<u>Class I (12 students)</u>	
Scholarships	22,050
Insurance	1,535
Tuition	1,200
Books	1,440
 <u>Class II (13 students)</u>	
Scholarships	24,115
Books	1,560
Travel (from home country to C.R.)	6,100
TOTAL	58,000

NOTE: UNA is providing the administration, professors and facilities for implementation of the graduate program.

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